

Synthesis of metal complexes with formyl- and acetylthiosemicarbazide

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Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} form 1 : 1 complexes with 1-formyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (FTSC) and 1-acetyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (ATSC); but Co^{II} forms 1 : 2 complex. All the complexes are non-electrolytes, and polymeric due to coordination by oxygen, sulphur and two nitrogen atoms. The ligand FTSC is a monobasic acid.

Thiosemicarbazide derivatives have antiviral and anti-tumor activities^{1,2}. 1-Acetyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (ATSC) is an useful intermediate for drugs and agrochemicals³. The Re^V complexes of ATSC have been reported⁴. Coordinating properties of acylthiosemicarbazides towards the 3d-metal ions appear interesting, and hence we undertook the present study.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are stable to air and moisture, coloured (except the Zn^{II} complex), insoluble in most of the common polar and nonpolar organic solvents and sparingly soluble in DMF and DMSO. Their conductance values (9–20 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) in DMSO (1 × 10⁻³ M) indicate non-electrolytic nature. The elemental analyses correspond to a metal : ligand ratio 1 : 1 for the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, but that for the Co^{II} complex is 1 : 2.

The thermogram of Co^{II}-FTSC complex shows weight-loss in three steps. A sudden weight-loss at 100° may be due to the loss of two moles of lattice water. The total weight-loss upto 450° is 82% and equals to two moles of the ligand, indicating 1 : 2 composition of the complex, [(Co(FTSC)₂)]·2H₂O. A similar thermogram was found for the Co^{II}-ATSC complex. Gradual weight-loss occurs in the range 200–500° for Ni^{II}- and Cu^{II}-FTSC complexes and in the range 100–800° for Zn^{II}-FTSC complex. The total weight-loss corresponds to one mole of the ligand, indicating 1 : 1 composition of the complexes.

Ir spectra of the ligands FTSC and ATSC have peaks characteristic for ν_{NH} [NH₂, NH (amide), NHCS], $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ and for $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and NH deformation and bending modes. The spectra of the complexes indicate the loss of the amide proton, since the ν_{NH} (amide) observed at 3100 cm⁻¹ in the ligands is absent in the spectra of the complexes. An extra peak⁵ develops at 1620–1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N) in the complexes. pH metric study⁶ in 70% (v/v) aqueous DMF medium and 0.1 M (KNO₃) indicates that FTSC is monoba-

sic acid with pK_a of 9.22 ± 0.06. These studies in presence of metal ions gave evidence for deprotonation of FTSC on complex formation. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ligand band is not observed in the complexes and an extra peak corresponding to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ is observed, thus indicating deprotonation of amide proton from oxygen in the enol form. ¹H nmr studies of the ligands adduce evidence for the keto-enol tautomerism. The $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ (NHCS) in the complexes is lowered, indicating that the nitrogen adjacent to thioketo group participates in bonding and thus forms a five-membered ring. Further, the shift in $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ in all the complexes except that of Co^{II}, indicates the participation of S of thioketo group in bonding.

The observed magnetic moments for Cu^{II}-FTSC and Cu^{II}-ATSC complexes (1.49 and 1.55 B.M.) indicate distorted octahedral geometry⁷. In Ni^{II}-FTSC and Ni^{II}-ATSC complexes, the observed moments 2.79 and 2.76 B.M. respectively, correspond to the spin-only value. The moments observed for the Co^{II} complexes (3.46 and 3.39 B.M.) are lower than expected (4.2–5.2 B.M.)⁸ and may be due to extensive spin-orbit coupling.

The esr spectra of Cu^{II}-FTSC and Cu^{II}-ATSC complexes show three g values indicating anisotropy. The g_x values of 2.148 and 2.282, g_y values 2.007 and 2.2167 and g_z values at 2.061 and 2.120 respectively, indicate lower symmetry at the metal ion⁹.

Experimental

The metal salts and other chemicals were of A. R. grade. Solvents such as methanol, ethanol and petroleum ether were purified¹⁰.

Formyl- and acetylthiosemicarbazides (FTSC and ATSC) were prepared by boiling thiosemicarbazide with an aliphatic carboxylic acid¹¹. The spectral data are as follows : FTSC ν_{max} 3381, 3292 (NH₂), 3187 (NH), 3100 (CONH), 2960 (C-H), 1685 (C=O), 1298 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 7.1 (2H, b, NH₂), 7.3 (1H, b, NH), 7.5 (1H, s, SH), 7.9–8.1 (1H, b, NH), 9.1–9.3 (1H, d, amide NH), 9.4 (1H, s,

OH), 9.7 (1H, s, H-CO); ATSC ν_{\max} 3442, 3280 (NH₂), 3167 (NH), 3100 (CONH), 2968 (C-H), 1600 (C=O), 1263 (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 3.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1 (2H, b, NH₂), 7.6 (1H, s, SH), 8.3 (1H, b, NH), 9.4 (1H, b, amide NH), 9.6 (1H, s, OH).

The complexes were synthesized using the ligands and metal chlorides (MCl₂). To a hot ethanolic solution of the ligand FTSC/ATSC (0.01 M), an aqueous solution of the respective metal salt (0.005 M) was added while stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 13–15 h to get the respective solid metal complexes (pH 4–7). The complexes were washed with ethanol and other solvents, followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and dried under reduced pressure. Elemental analyses of the complexes were found satisfactory for the composition [CoL₂].2H₂O and [MLCl]_n (M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}).

The metal contents were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. C, H and N analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 240 C analyser. The standard volumetric and gravimetric procedures were also used¹². Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method¹². Conductivity was measured on a Digisun D1 909 instrument at room temperature. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 435 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Bruker WH (270 MHz) spectrom-

eter and esr spectra on a Joel SE 3X (X band) (LNT) instrument. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Faraday 7550 balance. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were conducted on a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 instrument in the temperature range 50–800°.

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